

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF TINCTURE OF *SPHAERANTHUS INDICUS* (L) BY CO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS

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ABSTRACT

Tinctures of *Sphaeranthus indicus* were prepared by using 30 to 100 percent v/v ethyl alcohol by maceration process for 10, 20 and 30 days. Maximum yield of total solid content having pH 6.10 with specific gravity 0.99 and brown colour was recorded on 30th day of maceration at concentration of 30 percent v/v alcohol. Such effective tincture can be prepared and utilize for preparation of antiseptic ointment and other formulation.

KEY WORDS: Compositae, Co-chemical characterisation, *Sphaeranthus indicus*, Tincture.

INTRODUCTION

Sphaeranthus indicus (Linn) is a member of family *Compositae*, commonly known as Ghorakmundi is abundantly found in southern part of India especially in damp and in cultivated fields after harvest. It also found in the Himalayas up to an altitude of 5000 feet from Kumaon to Sikkim (Gogate 2000). It is extensively used in Ayurvedic medicine as tonic, cooling, alternative, antihelmintic, and in the treatment of styptic and gastric disorders. The pest prepared from roots and the aerial part is useful in skin diseases. It is also useful in the treatment of cough, in glandular swelling, urethral discharges, jaundice, indigestion, scabies and in remedy of piles and nerves depression (Chopra et al., 1986; Kirtikar 1987). Recently antibacterial activity of benzene extract of *Sphaeranthus indicus* was reported by Mahajan et al., (1998) and suggested that it is due to 7-hydroxy flrullanoied (Naqvi et al., 1985). An immunostimulant activity of sesquiterpene glycoside, Speranthanolide has been reported from the flower of *Sphaeranthus indicus* by Shekhani et al., (1990). Hence, taking into consideration the topical application of *Sphaeranthus indicus* in various bacterial and skin diseases, present investigation was undertaken to formulate an effective tincture with different co-chemical characteristics viz, total yield of solid, change in pH, specific gravity, and colour with effective period required for preparation of tincture.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The plant material was collected from North Maharashtra regions, (India) Viz. Toranmal plateau, Dondiacha, Sakri and Nandurbar district during the month of November to January 1996 – 1998 and identified in Botany Department of College. The whole plant material was dried under shed and pulverised by grinder and passed through 40 – mesh sieve. Absolute ethyl alcohol was used for preparation of different dilutions along with distilled water. Ten grams of the powdered plant material was taken in each of 24 amber coloured glass containers having 200-ml capacity. 100 ml solution of strength 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, and 100 percent v/v ethyl alcohol were prepared and taken in a separate, three sets of eight bottles. They were kept for maceration for 10, 20, and 30 days-respective (Nairn and Kennedy 1980). The material was filtered under reduced pressure through sintered funnel. Each experiment was repeated thrice. In all cases the colour, pH, specific gravity, and total solid content in the tincture were measured (Gennaro 1980). The tincture producing highest yield was subjected to standard phytochemical analyses for different constituents (Trease and Evans, 1983). The presence of alkaloids, glycosides, tannins, saponins and anthraquinones were tested.

RESULTS

All the tinctures were clear liquid without any turbidity or sedimentation. The colour of the

alcoholic solution of different strength was varies as seen in the table - 1. The variation of pH from 5.53 to 6.25 was recorded in different grades of tinctures (Table - 2). Minimum total solid matter was recorded in 100 percent (v/v) alcoholic solution, while it was maximum in 30 percent (v/v) alcohol (Table - 3) highest specific gravity was

recorded in 30 percent (v/v) alcoholic solution, and it was minimum in 100 percent (v/v) alcohol (Table - 4). Phytochemical tests viz. Libermann Burchard reaction, Carr - Price reagent test showed the presence of triterpenoids (triterpenes, sterol, saponin, sapogenins) in the 30 percent (v/v) tincture, while test for alkaloid was found to be negative with Dragandroff reagent.

Table 1: Colour of different tinctures

Strength (% v/v)	Colour of the tincture
30.0	Brown
40.0	yellowish brown
50.0	yellowish brown
60.0	Greenish brown
70.0	yellowish green

Table 2: pH of different tincture at various duration of maceration.

Strength (% v/v)	pH Duration of Maceration		
	10 days	20 days	30 days
30.00	5.80	6.02	6.10
40.00	6.07	6.19	6.20
50.00	6.08	6.13	6.23
60.00	6.20	6.25	6.26
70.00	6.16	6.19	6.20
80.00	6.16	6.18	6.22
90.00	6.04	6.07	6.10
100.00	5.53	5.71	5.91

Table 3: Solid matter content of different tincture at various duration of maceration.

Strength (% v/v)	Solid matter content (gm / 5 ml)		
	Duration of Maceration		
	10 days	20 days	30 days
30.00	0.1670	0.1710	0.8113
40.00	0.1421	0.1447	0.1591
50.00	0.1331	0.1396	0.1410
60.00	0.1236	0.1221	0.1393
70.00	0.1142	0.1195	0.1273
80.00	0.1007	0.1074	0.1197
90.00	0.0811	0.0848	0.0989
100.00	0.0613	0.0712	0.0793

DISCUSSION:

The colour of different tinctures varies with different strength of alcohol's from brown to dark green, but it has no effect on duration of

maceration. This is due to maximum extraction of the constituents present in them. The variation of pH of the tincture depending on their duration of maceration was quit distinct. This may be due to the

Table 4: Specific gravity of different tincture at various duration of maceration. Strength (% v/v)

	Specific gravity		
	Duration of Maceration		
	10 days	20 days	30 days
30.00	0.9497	0.9763	0.9938
40.00	0.9328	0.9509	0.9852
50.00	0.9192	0.9461	0.9623
60.00	0.8912	0.9474	0.9561
70.00	0.8612	0.9172	0.9171
80.00	0.8224	0.8993	0.8921
90.00	0.8102	0.8654	0.8501
100.00	0.8004	0.8312	0.8424

variation of total solid content and the chemical constituents present in them. The variation in the specific gravity of the tinctures depending on the percent strength of the alcohol was found to be correlates with the total solid matter, which was maximum at a concentration of 30 percent (v/v) alcohol on 30 days of maceration. This indicates that for maximum extraction less amount of alcohol is required which solublies high amount of plant constituents in presence of water. So it is evident that 30 percent (v/v) ethyl alcohol and 30 day period was suitable for extraction of maximum amount of soluble constituents containing phyto-chemicals such as Terpenoids, sterols, saponin, glycosides. As literature survey shows that plant products of *Sphaeranthus indicus* is effective on skin diseases (Kapoor 1992; Turner, 1998), preparation of an antiseptic ointment using this tincture of *Sphaeranthus indicus* and its clinical trial is in progress.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are thankful to the authority of HPT Arts & RYK Science College, Nashik, D.B.F.Dayanand college of Arts and Science, Solapur. and the Staff of Botany Department for the identification of plant material.

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